

Table 1: Primary Studies

ID	Title	Proposal	Stage of the life cycle	QA	RQ
S1	A Deployment Model to Extend Ethically Aligned AI Implementation Method ECCOLA	methodology	software requirements; software design; software construction;	4.0	2
S2	From ethical AI frameworks to tools: a review of approaches	analysis	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.5	3
S3	A framework for assessing AI ethics with applications to cybersecurity	framework	software requirements	3.5	1 e 2
S4	All that glitters is not gold: trustworthy and ethical AI principles	framework	software requirements	3.5	2
S5	A Rapid Review of Responsible AI frameworks: How to guide the development of ethical AI	analysis	-	4.0	3
S6	AI Ethics Impact Assessment based on Requirement Engineering	methodology	software requirements	5.0	2
S7	Z-Inspection: A Process to Assess Trustworthy AI	process	planning; software maintenance and deploy	5.0	2
S8	Implementing AI Ethics: Making Sense of the Ethical Requirements	principles	-	2.5	1
S9	How Do Software Companies Deal with Artificial Intelligence Ethics? A Gap Analysis	analysis	-	4.5	1
S10	Governance of Ethical and Trustworthy AI Systems: Research Gaps in the ECCOLA Method	method	-	4.5	2
S11	Ethical Requirements Stack: A framework for implementing ethical requirements of AI in software engineering practices	framework	software requirements	3.0	2 e 3
S12	Implementing AI Ethics in a Software Engineering Project-Based Learning Environment - The Case of WIMMA Lab	framework	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	2.5	2
S13	AI Ethics Principles in Practice: Perspectives of Designers and Developers	process	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction	5.5	2
S14	Beyond 100 Ethical Concerns in the Development of Robot-to-Robot Cooperation	framework	-	3.5	2

S15	What Is the Cost of AI Ethics? Initial Conceptual Framework and Empirical Insights	framework	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction	5.0	2
S16	Ethics of AI: A systematic literature review of principles and challenges	analysis	-	3.5	1
S17	Ethics by Design for Intelligent and Sustainable Adaptive Systems	framework	software construction	5.5	2
S18	Designing Up with Value-Sensitive Design: Building a Field Guide for Ethical ML Development	tool	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	6.0	2 e 3
S19	A participatory data-centric approach to AI Ethics by Design	process	planning; software requirements; software design; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.5	2
S20	AI Ethics for Industry 5.0 – From Principles to Practice	framework	software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	3.0	2 e 3
S21	Putting AI Ethics into Practice: The Hourglass Model of Organizational AI Governance	methodology	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.0	2
S22	How Do AI Ethics Principles Work? From Process to Product Point of View	analysis	-	4.0	1 e 3
S23	The Different Faces of AI Ethics Across the World: A Principle-to-Practice Gap Analysis	analysis	-	5.0	3
S24	Measuring Ethics in AI with AI: A Methodology and Dataset Construction	tool	software construction	4.0	-
S25	Governance of Artificial Intelligence – A Framework Towards Ethical AI Applications	framework	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	3.5	2
S26	Worldwide AI Ethics: a review of 200 guidelines and recommendations for AI governance	tool	-	5.5	1

S27	ECCOLA — A method for implementing ethically aligned AI systems	method	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.0	2 e 3
S28	The Importance of an Ethical Framework for Trust Calibration in AI	framework	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	4.0	2
S29	The Role of Explainable AI in the Research Field of AI Ethics	analysis	-	4.0	1
S30	Towards a Roadmap on Software Engineering for Responsible AI	analysis	-	5.0	3
S31	Governance in Ethical, Trustworthy AI Systems: Extension of the ECCOLA Method for AI Ethics Governance Using GARP	method	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.0	2
S32	Fairness Score and process standardization: framework for fairness certification in artificial intelligence systems	framework	software construction	4.5	2
S33	From AI ethics principles to data science practice: a reflection and a gap analysis based on recent frameworks and practical experience	analysis	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	3.5	3
S34	Fairness in Design: A Tool for Guidance in Ethical Artificial Intelligence Design	framework	software requirements	4.0	2 e 3
S35	Putting AI ethics to work: are the tools fit for purpose?	analysis	-	4.5	2
S36	Transparency and explainability of AI systems: From ethical guidelines to requirements	analysis	software requirements	5.0	1 e 3
S37	Responsible AI Pattern Catalogue: A Collection of Best Practices for AI Governance and Engineering	process	planning; software requirements; software design; software construction; software testing; software maintenance and deploy	5.0	2
S38	Ethical Guidelines and Principles in the Context of Artificial Intelligence	analysis	-	4.0	1